

RESPONSE PAPER

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PROGRAM CODE: PHGH
COURSE CODE: ACA-401D
PERIOD NUMBER: 6
INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is <18%

The author used the following software: Windows 11

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D RP6

1. The structure of the essay should be in the following format:

- Question: Research the topic and Take notes from your preliminary reading
- Researching the Topic, Analyzing the question, and establish the points of view
- Organizing your Ideas, Writing the Essay, and Referencing the Essay
- Introduction, Body, and Conclusion.**¹

2. What is Plagiarism?

¹ Laurent Cleenewerk and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fifth Edition. (Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2024), 10.

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- Take someone else's words or ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from the Internet, and whether to give credit to the author.
 - Do not take someone's job and give them credit.
 - When the writer uses a source of information without crediting the author of that source of information.²**
 - When using any quotes, paraphrases, statistics/data, or visuals (such as a graph) that are borrowed from another source, but quotes correctly
3. **In every research project, there are an infinite number of specific tasks; however, in all research projects, you have only five general objectives; of the following, identify the false one:**
- Ask a question that is worth answering.
 - Find an answer that can be backed up with good reasons
 - Find and use good data as reliable evidence to support your reasons
 - Not reviewing the draft thoroughly until readers think you met the first four objectives.³**
4. **It is essential to evaluate the research questions because not all questions are good. Therefore, you should avoid questions such as the following:**
- Their answers are facts that you could look up.

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, 34-39.

³ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th edition, Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing (Chicago; London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 23.

- Your answers cannot be plausibly refuted and require more or different resources—materials, technology, money, especially time—than you have.
- Their answers would be merely speculative and are dead ends.
- All the above.**⁴

5. **What is the main difference between practical problems and conceptual problems in a research problem?**

- The cost of a practical problem always has a tangible effect
- Practical problems do have a tangible cost
- A conceptual problem is a lack of understanding
- Practical problems refer to what we must do, and conceptual problems refer to what we should think.**⁵

6. **Regarding punctuation, indicate what italics are used for.**

- For emphasis on words that are not in the original.**⁶
- If you need to insert one or more words of explanation, clarification, or correction in a quotation
- If you cite a passage that includes a superscript note number
- If you omit words, phrases, sentences, or even paragraphs from a quotation

⁴ Turabian et al., 28.

⁵ Turabian et al., 29.

⁶ Turabian et al., 376.

7. Of the following options, choose which is the most appropriate for the meaning of the epigraph?

- A recognition of someone who has been especially important to you.
- It is a personal expression in which the author dedicates his work to one or more people, showing gratitude, affection, or recognition.
- A personal gesture by the author towards people or causes that he considers important.
- A quote that establishes the theme of the paper is usually its most appropriate use when its words are especially impactful and uniquely capture the spirit of its work.⁷

8. What are the Components of Dissertation Research? Ideally, students prepare the following dissertation documents:

- Dissertation concept paper, Dissertation prospectus, Dissertation and Dissertation manuscript.⁸
- Dissertation concept paper, Dissertation prospectus, Pre-prospectus paper, and Dissertation manuscript
- Dissertation manuscript, Dissertation, Statement of the Problem and Dissertation concept paper

⁷ Turabian et al., 401.

⁸ James P. Sampson Jr, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 9.

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- Dissertation Prospectus, The Dissertation, The Dedication and Dissertation concept paper

9. Regarding the Overview of Research Paradigms, it mentions what is the strategy/tradition/genre of the qualitative methodology inquiry:

- Descriptive, correlational, causal/comparative, and experimental research
- Case study, grounded theory, ethnography, narrative inquiry, discourse analysis, phenomenology, action research, postmodernism, and poststructuralism.⁹
- Seek range and variation in findings and delve into the “essence” of the topic
- The survey includes closed-ended questions, scales, and ranking order checklists

10. According to the WHO’s style guide, which of the following statements is the most appropriate

- Never use internal, abbreviated WHO names in any text for an external audience.
For example: World Health Organization, WHO, the Organization (*not* World Health Organization, the WHO).
- Structure: WHO Member States are grouped into six regions, each of which has a decision-making body (a regional committee) and a regional office with a regional director.

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⁹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 4th ed. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2019), 140.

- Politically and legally sensitive topics: Offensive statements pass subjective judgements on countries or their political systems, activities or historical background (by, for example, using such terms as “underdeveloped countries” or the “Third World”).
- D) All of the above are correct.¹⁰

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie F. Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. 4th ed. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2019.

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WHO. *WHO Style Guide*. 2nd ed. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

¹⁰ WHO, *WHO Style Guide Second Edition*, KMS/WHP/13.1 (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2013), 3–6.

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